

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

BALANCING PERSONALISED LEARNING WITH THE DOGME ELT FRAMEWORK FOR DEVELOPING COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS: A CASE STUDY IN ARMENIAN CLASS

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Abstract

In the evolving landscape of language learning and teaching, it is of high relevance to use methods that not only foster effective language acquisition but also engage students by addressing their individual needs and interests. This study explores the integration of Dogme ELT (Teaching Unplugged) and personalized learning strategies within an English as a Foreign Language (EFL) context, aiming to increase student engagement, communicative competence, and motivation in shaping their own learning track. By blending these approaches, the research examines how a dynamic, learner-centered environment can be attained at the same time not completely denying traditional course materials, such as textbooks, and the integration of digital tools as well. The study has been conducted with a group of 20 high school students, who partook in a controlled experiment comparing the traditional coursebook-based lesson environment with a more flexible, interactive and harmonious approach that combined coursebooks, Dogme ELT principles. The resultant data displayed significant uplift in learners engagement, language fluency and communicative competence when Dogme ELT and personalised learning strategies are enacted. These results underline the significance of adapting teaching philosophy to better suit multifaceted needs of students in today's highly developed digital age.

Keywords: Dogme ELT, personalised learning and teaching, integrated approach, dynamic environment, learner-centered, experimental study, student engagement, unplugged teaching, individual needs, learning track, etc..

Introduction

In the ever developing world of teaching and learning it has become much challenging to spark the interest of the students and organize fruitful lessons. Teachers have a wide range of methods and tremendous amount of lesson materials at their disposal to conduct lessons that are scripted in a way that meets the needs of each student as well as to construct a dynamic and engaging leaning environment. The overreliance of coursebooks and the topics that are not closely connected to each other has led to the implementation of Dogme ELT approach which places learners at the centre of their learning journey, recognising the interests and supplying them with close to real-world crafted lessons to foster genuine communication. Accordingly we've tried to craft a well-balanced learning and teaching way to incorporate Dogme ELT along with personalised learning without denying the complete use of coursebooks thus trying to implement digital tool mainly because it's paramount to grasp students interests.

Research Methods

Comparative analysis, statistical analysis, deductive method, inductive method, descriptive method, questionnaire, case study.

Statement of the problem

The main highlight of the research is that implementing Dogme ELT means that the students are to participate in shaping their educational experience thus assisting the educators to help to build their own individual track of learning. It is of great importance to equip

learners with efficacious language learning that lies in a well-balanced approach, thus engaging students with meaningful communication practice (Cazden 1992)

The goal of this research is to explore the outcomes of applying a blended approach that combines the Dogme ELT framework with personalised learning strategies in an EFL context. The integration of these two approaches leads to measurable improvements in learner motivation, communicative competence, and individualized language development.

Research Questions

The current study aims to answer the following questions;

1. Whether the implementation of Dogme ELT along with the personalized learning approach enhances students engagement in the learning process
2. How can Dogme ELT be utilised in classrooms with the combination of coursebooks and digital tools.

Theoretical background

As it can be viewed from the current trends, besides the diachronic analysis of English Language teaching methodologies reveal a progression which displays that educators move from traditional teacher centered approaches to more innovative, communicative methods which not only fosters students communicative competence but also makes them more engaged in the learning process. (Fries C. C 1954).It's worth mentioning that educators of 21st century don't solely focus on one approach or method but rather navigate a blend of approaches trying to tailor their teaching way to the specific learning context and what is more important to

the unique needs of their students. In order to create a dynamic, effective and engaging learning environment we have tried to incorporate two cutting edge approaches together which are personalised learning and Dogme ELT (unplugged teaching) In the recent years personalised learning has gone through renewal of interests as for now personalised learning presents a significant paradigm shift in educational context uplifting from teacher-centered to learner-centered approach. It is paramount to analyse the foundation of personalised learning which lies in understanding individual needs and preferences of students that is why the Universal Design of Learning framework is initiated. The latter emphasises three key facets which can be recruited in "What, Why, How" questions.

Representation: this provides learners with diverse ways to access and process information. This supports the "What" of learning.

Engagement: This allocates strategies to leverage student's interests and "why of learning" which is responsible for students motivation and engagement in the learning process.

Expression and Action: this addresses to "How" of learning which is related to how students perform tasks, organize and express their ideas (Cast 2018).

This approach is directly connected to one of the current teaching philosophies that is Dogme ELT or Unplugged teaching.

Interestingly enough the term Dogme first originated in the context of cinema. It was brought to life by the Danish directors Lars Von Trier and Thomas Vinterberg, who set up a Dogme 95 movement, which aimed to eliminate artificial effects and paying more attention on the meaning and message of the film. The movement concentrated on telling a story with no post production and utilizing actual settings (Vinterberg, T., & von Trier, L. (1995). *Dogme 95*)

Scott Thornbury inspired by this human-centric philosophy initiated Dogme ELT in 2000. He believed that education had reached a point of over-reliance on technological and physical resources. Teaching Unplugged (Meddings & Thornbury, 2009), published seven years later, highlights three main principles of the approach:

- **Conversation driven:** Conversation is the heart of communications, thus it provides discourse. Students craft coherent, connected sentences that builds upon previous statements and construct meaning relevant to the topic. Moreover conversation is considered to be both process and the product of the language. Lessons should be architected the way that students get valuable speaking practice and communicative competence through the use of vocabulary and grammar constructions as well thus creating meaningful speech. Conversation is of great significance as it is language at work, it is discourse, *conversation is interactive, dialogic and communicative along with the fact that conversation scaffolds learning.* . (Meddings & Thornbury 2009 p.8)

- **Materials-light:** the following principle based on being conversation driven naturally limits the use of

materials, upholding the content that strives from the conversation. This, however does not meet that the use of textbooks are denied or the lesson should be completely unplugged. Dogme ELT approach challenges the overreliance of the textbooks mainly because they do not target individual learner needs, thus creating unnatural interaction opportunities and sometimes even blocking interaction together (Meddings, L., & Thornbury, S. (2009). It is worth highlighting that Dogme ELT encourages to craft a well balanced and integrated approach using textbooks as meaningful source along with digital tools and personalised learning principles as well.

- **Emergent language:** The main philosophy behind this principle is the condition where students are equipped with optimal conditions of language use and more significantly are motivated to take ownership of these opportunities this will lead to the activation of inherent learning capacities, and language instead of being acquired will emerge. (Meddings, L., & Thornbury, S. 2010)

Dogme ELT, a communicative language teaching approach pioneered by Scott Thornbury, emphasizes conversation-driven instruction, emergent language, and minimal reliance on pre-designed materials. One of its main advantages is its adaptability to learners' individual needs, fostering greater learner engagement and personalization (Thornbury, 2009). As lessons emerge from authentic classroom interaction, students often experience more meaningful and relevant language use. Moreover, the approach encourages spontaneity and responsiveness from the teacher, aligning well with learner-centered pedagogy (Meddings & Thornbury, 2009). However, Dogme ELT also presents several challenges. Without structured materials, inexperienced teachers may struggle with lesson planning and classroom management, leading to inconsistent learning outcomes (Waters, 2012). Additionally, some learners especially those who are accustomed to traditional, grammar-focused instruction may find the approach disorienting or insufficient for exam preparation (Harmer, 2014). Despite these drawbacks, Dogme ELT offers a dynamic alternative to textbook-heavy methodologies, especially when used by skilled practitioners who can balance flexibility with pedagogical structure.

Recognising the shared values of Dogme ELT approach and personalised learning an experiment is held to develop students communicative skills as well as their engagement in the lesson process.

Participants:

This case study was conducted with the help of 20 students from the High School of Shirak State University. They were studying at the 11th grade (Humanities Stream). These learners' age were ranging from 16 to 17 years old. To achieve the objectives of the study and to understand students hobbies and interests a questionnaire has been given to them which comprises questions about their favourite free time activities, the fields that they want to use English, the way they prefer learn

English and how confident they are while speaking English. After the questionnaire the student were given a pre-test to evaluate their general speaking abilities (accuracy and fluency). After the post-test the students were randomly divided into two groups of control (n=10) and experimental (n=10). The control group lesson was held based on the coursebook materials solely whereas experimental group lesson was held based on a well-balanced approach incorporating coursebook materials along with digital tools with the implementation of Dogme ELT and personalised learning and teaching philosophy.

Instrumentation:

To conduct this study several instruments were utilised. At first students took an individual track questionnaire which consisted of 10 questions to reveal students real interests which are closely connected to English language learning and the future use of it for various purposes

(to access the questionnaire scan the QR code)

The second instrument was composed of a pre-test of speaking to check learners' accuracy and fluency. For the control group lesson 11th grade coursebook was used whereas for the experimental group along with the coursebook a brainstorming tool was implemented and later students used a digital tool to create a logo for their speech presentation. The post-test that was applied after conducting lessons with control and experimental groups was the same as the pre-test in order to get accurate data and see the outcomes of incorporating Dogme ELT approach balanced with personalised learning and teaching.

(scan the QR codes to access the pre-test activities)

Materials:

Materials that were applied during the lesson were based on Unit 10 "TV or not TV" from students coursebook (English 11, S. Baghdassarian, S. Gurdjayants). Later a brainstorming tool was utilised for the experimental group to collect information about their associations with the lesson topic. Then students were given autonomy to form groups inside the EG to present their unique ideas connected to the lesson topic.

Procedure

The first step of the research study was to give an individual track questionnaire to students to get genuine results about their interests and fields of future studies. Then a pre-test was administered. The first activity of the pre-test, worth 2 points, was based on the previously learned units from the coursebook presented by a question wheel made by a "Wordwall" website. The second activity of the pre-test which consisted of 2 parts, worth 6 and 2 points respectively, was based on the CEFR topics to assess students abilities in general communicative topics to see how they can speak and collaborate with each other. Students were to role-play real-life scenarios (asking for a direction in a foreign country, shopping and asking about the prices and so on). The second part of the activity was to enroll students into a free discussion on personal questions. It has already been stated students were randomly divided in two equal groups for control and experimental studies. As it can be implied the lesson with the control group was held using coursebook materials only without trying to personalise or unplug the lesson. The topic of the lesson was TV. Students read a short passage about TV and answered the questions based on the text. Then, they did two vocabulary exercises about different types of TV programmes. This is all what was appended in the lesson part in line with the coursebook unit. To conduct the EG lesson the same unit was taken as our aim was not to deny the usage of coursebook but to use it as a supportive resource prioritizing students engagement and interaction, whereas several modifications were done to architect the lesson according to Dogme ELT approach. The lesson started by reading the text from the textbook and answering general questions about TV.

In order to understand the level of engagement in the lesson topic a brainstorming activity was introduced where students wrote their associations with the word TV. After discussing their associations students offered to form group and try to create an appealing advertisement that people will not want to skip while watching TV, however 3 students offered to act the jury to assess other 2 groups. Thereby 3 groups were formed from 10 students.

Group 1: 3 of the students who were deeply interested in travelling and learning languages decided to make an advertisement of a language school and show how important it is to know English while travelling. To make it more vivid they roleplayed 3 different situations on asking and giving directions, ordering food, asking a travel guide information about the place they are visiting. After the role-play they started to advertise their ideas of a language school which was named MotivEng (Motivation+English) by them.

Group 2: 4 of the students offered to show a new film review and try to attract the audience. It became evident from the ideas that they were interested in learning the language through films and videos, so this gave a soil for them to offer such kind of advertisement. Students introduced the concept, the target audience the unique features of their film as well thus trying to attract the viewers .

Group 3: 3 students suggested acting as the jury. They decided to evaluate the pitches from the other

groups based on creativity, persuasiveness, originality, and how engaging the idea would be for a TV audience. They have even created criteria for evaluation.

After organizing lessons with both control and experimental groups learners were asked to do the post-test. There were some minor modifications in the post test which was similar to the pre-test to get precise data.

Research Findings

Based on the goal of the study which was about whether the implementation of Dogme ELT along with the personalized learning approach enhances students engagement in the learning process and how can

Dogme ELT be utilised in classrooms along with coursebooks and digital tools.

The participants of the study passed a pre-test as well as a post-test after having organized the lessons with control and experimental groups. In order to get precise data students are assessed for communicative competence (accuracy and fluency). The scoring system was adapted from Brown 2004 and CEFR speaking skill descriptors.

The following table displays the data analysis generated from the pre-test and post-test administered to CG students.

Table 1

Classification	Score	Pre-Test		Post-Test	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Excellent	9-10	1	10%	1	10%
Very good	7-8	2	20%	3	30%
Good	5-6	4	40%	4	40%
Average	3-4	1	10%	1	10%
Poor	1-2	2	20%	1	10%
Total		10	100%	10	100%

As it can be observed from Table 1 there has been a slight rise in the number of students classified as very good whereas the number of students getting excellent and good results has remained the same. On the other

hand the number of students receiving poor results has decreased to 10%.

To illustrate the changes vividly bar graph is introduced based on Table 1 data.

Figure 1. Comparative results of the analysis (CG)

The mean score of the CG is depicted below.

Table 2

Test	Mean Score
Pre-test	5,8
Post-test	6,4
Different	0,6

With a view to observe the outcomes of the EG the table and bar graph are presented.

Experimental group

Table 3

Classification	Score	Pre-test		Post-test	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Excellent	9-10	1	10%	2	20%
Very good	7-8	1	10%	2	20%
Good	5-6	2	20%	4	40%
Average	3-4	4	40%	1	10%
Poor	1-2	2	20%	1	10%
Total		10	100%	10	100%

Figure 2

From the results it can be inferred that there has been a considerable change in the number of students classified as good and average with 20% growth and 30% fall respectively which conclusively demonstrates the usefulness of the experimental group's technology.

In addition, moderate changes of 10% are seen with students classified as excellent, very good and poor. Thus efficacious rises and falls are estimated in the table for all classifications.

Figure 3. The mean score comparison of EG and CG

It can be seen from the graph that the difference of the mean score in EG group is considerably higher than that of CG group. The both groups have recorded an upward trend, however, the results of EG group are more than three times higher in relation to CG group. These results are to show the high efficacy of the incorporation of Dogme ELT with personalized learning in teaching and learning practice develop speaking skills as well as to increase students interaction and ownership in building their own individual track in learning.

Conclusion

This study disposes impact of integrating the Dogme ELT approach with personalized learning philosophy in an EFL context, focusing on student engagement, communicative competence, and the efficacy of blending traditional coursebook materials with digital tools. The findings of the research stipulate that the explicit implementation of Dogme ELT and personalized learning enhances student's engagement of the lesson

process and facilitates the possibility of building their individual track in learning.

The case study provided an outstanding opportunity to see the student's engagement in the lessons. Through the case study conducted with high school students, it became evident that learners engaged in lessons orchestrated by their interests and personal learning preferences validated higher levels of motivation, creativity, and communicative competence.

A flexible, integrated and learner-centered approach which was closely based on student's interest incorporating authentic language use and highly elevated learner's motivation and engagement. The experimental group where the above mentioned approaches were executed outperformed the control group in both pre and post-test assessments. Thus, displaying the point that the constructive integration of Dogme ELT in parallel with coursebook content and digital tools,

brainstorming activities, and real-life simulations fostered authentic interaction, refining fluency and accuracy, and encouraging students to take ownership of their learning journey.

Ultimately, the implementation of Dogme ELT aspects with personalised learning reveals the synergy between these two approaches which in its turn creates dynamic, engaging and individualized approach. This brings to the insight that it requires a continuous professional development from the teachers perspective as well thus the approaches provide a valuable alternative for educators who seek to perfect their teaching style striving to find a well-balanced, technology enhanced close to real life teaching philosophy.

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